

Developing the Thought on Students Migration (Which Here Termed As Brain Drain) From Rural Parts of West Bengal and Its Lasting Impact on Society As Well As On the State for Gainful Research: An Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT- In general parlance, the present study is an attempt to understand the root causes behind student migration from rural parts of West Bengal and its overall impacts on society as well as on the state. The number of students migrate from rural parts of Bengal is increasing tremendously. The aim and objective and ultimate preferences of studying outside the state, is that, students always prefer to get the option in which they are interested in and in which they want their specialization, which they might not be getting in their native colleges and Universities. The degree which they obtain from that universities or colleges from that states is considered to be worth when it comes to searching a good job in any place. The other benefit of obtaining the degree is most of the universities or colleges allow the students to go abroad for completing their final semester. A chance to get educated at any foreign land might be a distant dream for any middle class students. Moreover, apart from these factors there are some key factors like quality education, potential placement, a good standard of living, and especially a very poor job opportunities and lower pay scales in the domestic areas are among the most important reasons for thinking of migration. There is no doubt that the overall economic development of the rural parts of Bengal largely depends on the people, especially on the young generations to a great extent. If the generation leaves or migrate to other states for searching of a better future, It should be considered as brain drain of intellectual resource.

Therefore the study initially indicated that constant and comprehensive monitoring of the trend, and if possible a regular evaluation process has to be implemented in the educational institutions to observe the parameter of the trend. The trend cannot be eradicated permanently, until and unless State Government, Panchayet, Bank assistance (Easiest way to get Student's loan for higher studies), and above all a State-Central placement cell run and governed by affiliated Universities are not established immediately.

KEYWORDS: Migration, rural, education, development, urban

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent times West Bengal has been witnessing a substantial amount of students mainly from the rural parts of Bengal, moving to the other states basically for pursuing higher studies, and eventually settling there. Prolong lopsided governmental policies which was unable to pay attention to the young generation and their issues, was the key factors for the students migration. The researchers attributed the reasons behind the trend of young students leaving the state to other state only for lack of pre-determined governmental plan and policies in West Bengal. Several factors which appear to be accelerating the massive outflow of students beyond the west Bengal borders. The reasons can largely be divided into two broad groups:

- Massive development in the global sector. It includes factors like globalisation of education, Introducing new courses. Advance training and technological development, and adequate subsidization of education. (MOE-2020)
 - Domestic condition: It includes factors like huge gap between demand and supply of high education, Red tape barriers of education loan, and poor job opportunities along with very low salary structure, that force the students from rural parts of West Bengal to migrate to other states following which the loss of intellectual section of the society. (MHRD-2013)
- The study describes the trend of migration as a brain drain? Here brain drain includes loss of intellectual brain, talent, knowledge, skills and innovative ideas of the individuals. Now why the migration and brain drain happens? The major reasons are:

A. Immense rural poverty and economically constraints

The major population leaves here in rural parts. Therefore, the small hold family farmers, owing to land being limited, they do not get enough land to go for farming. So if a student from poor farmer's family wants to pursue his or her higher education and a decent job, which is difficult to get by crossing red tape philosophy, the migration to the other state is the only option left in front of the aspirant. So finding a good option, they prefer to leave their native place for improving their livelihood (truth fully-for higher education, good shelter and security) (King & Sondhi. 2018. Yang-2003)

B. Lack of employment and health security

Basically non development of the rural part of West Bengal and importantly income generating opportunities. It is no denying about the fact that all the agricultural related jobs are associated with low and unstable incomes, along with almost low living standards. So without getting a bare minimum income and health security, a substantial amount of young may get frustrated and decide to go for finding a better future (Ankrah Kwaku Twumasi (1995))

C. In fact, , inequality is the important issue

Our rural young generation are facing inequality issues. It is a normal trend the rural young people, always prefer to go urban areas of the developing metros because of better employment and for better professional educational purposes-like easy to get bare minimum employment, business opportunities, easy access to improved health facilities

D. Limited access to social protection-

About 70% or more than rural students has not adequate access to social protection. In the rural areas of the state, where the student face difficulties in managing social, economical justice and face environmental risks

E. The migration itself has a neighbourhood effect.

It means if a student in the neighbourhood or peer group goes to other state for higher education, it gradually becomes a chain action. The money which needs to be spent and courses available are shared among the peer groups- (News paper-The Hindu)

The trend to go outside, mainly abroad for pursuing higher education was concentrated only in the professional courses like MBBS, Law, engineering and for Phd etc, but in today it is observed that students were migrating at a very young stage, even after finishing higher secondary school education. As per government statement this migration resulted in over 15000 vacant seats in the state's engineering colleges and over few thousands seats were vacant in the management and science streams. (News Paper-The Hindu)

F. The government initiative is very low.

If the government give the best platform, increases the best infrastructure will be able to reduce migration and brain drain also.

The present study also evaluates the issues and observes, the West Bengal state government, especially in this context, a bit late, and has not yet awakened to the problem of massive exodus of students. On the other hand, considering the gravity of the issues, state government like Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Odissa have already started to set up EDU-BUSINESS, EDUCATIONAL CITIES and SPECIAL EDUCATION ZONES. (MHRD-2013) This set ups are providing all short facilities say from higher education facilities. providing easy bank loan and students credit card for higher education, experienced and renowned academicians, high ranking professional study centres and potential placement officer and cell, have triggered the rural mediocre students of West Bengal to migrate them to that states.

Hence the present study is just another attempt to contribute to the existing literature. Preventing migration in order to protect the brain drain is essential for the first generation of young students, particularly in the rural areas. Afsar Rita (2003). Promotion and development of the educational infrastructure is very much important for reducing migrant from rural parts of Bengal Deshingkar Priya (2004) . What could be the best measures to eradicate the trend of migration along with brain drain is stated with the bullet points:

- Emphasis for higher education - Through overall development programme in educational sectors from general to professional courses, and setting up the national council for educational research and training programmes, Prerana scheme for preparing SC/ST students for higher education.
- Balanced rural development- By setting small training and professional course unites in remote areas, can help balanced rural development, which help aspirant students not to go outside from their native place
- Harnessing locally available resources: Schools and colleges in the remote part of West Bengal could be most dependable locally available resources. The teachers of this institution can help in harnessing the locally available resources by training and educating prospective students(Gardner Katy & Ahmed Zahir (2006)
- Reduce social tensions-Establishing professional course units, colleges and schools in the remote village defuses social tension by providing self –employment careers to the talents of the educated youth
- Overall development – Efficient and effective use of limited resources by the local schools, colleges and universities leads to overall economic development of the rural part of west Bengal, and thus provides a great impact into the mind of the students for not going outside for persuasion of better education and lives(Katseli T. Louka, Lucas E.B. Robert & Xenogiani Theodora (2006)

- To establish a specific student credit card for those students who will study in west Bengal only.
- Setting up effective and progressive professional institution in every rural districts of West Bengal along with the facilities like Merit Based Admission, and entirely education fees waiver for the topper of the state.
 - Free entry without any stringent admission paraphernalia, no compensation fees would be allowed in the admission process
 - Setting up appropriate ambience with contemporary curriculum and impactful pedagogy
 - Setting up units of vocational training institution in every districts for providing training and skills development for the global exposure and placement opportunity.
 - Easy access to information and networking systems
 - Setting up one outstanding placement cell which will be comprises with good recruiters of the country
 - Setting up translational research centre for identifying the potential talent in the areas
 - All most all governmental schemes and programmes need to be given new thrust for the overall improvement of the state.
 - Setting up units associated with strong students engagement in social activates
- The study has pointed out one interesting way to counter these issues to highlight the charm of potential and higher education to the students. For which we need to identify those students who are having potentiality and see that their talents are nurtured. Special attention must be paid to the quality of teaching the subject. (Report on Migration by Department for International Development (2007))

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *King and Sondhi, 2018; Yang, 2003)*

But it is half of a story. Other components, viz., quality of resources (stimulating ICT classrooms and adequate teaching-learning materials), quality of teachers and curriculum, quality learners, quality learning environments and quality leadership, are equally important

B. *Ankrah Kwaku Twumasi (1995)*

Rural Urban Migration & Socioeconomic development in Ghana: This article discusses the case of Ghana, where rural urban Migration creates major change in social and behavioral pattern of migrant people when These migrants decide to shift their base due to availability of better education, healthcare Facilities and entertainment and then this force them to re-socialize their behaviours which ultimately leads to change in behavioral pattern.

C. *Afsar Rita (2003)*

Internal Migration & development Nexus – The Case of Bangladesh: The paper focuses on the core concept of rural – urban migration, which explains, that people move for better employment options as they are less dependent on agricultural sector. These migrants normally face job insecurity, poor working condition & discrimination in the urban work place. The paper also challenges the very basic fact that rural urban migration brings rural poverty to urban areas. The actual fact is that due to increase in remittances, savings rate as well as standard of living has improved remarkably.. And this becomes possible due to movement of people from less developed rural areas to well developed urban areas.

D. *Deshingkar Priya (2004)*

Understanding the Implications of Migration for Pro Poor Agricultural Growth: The paper highlights on the fact that increasing mobility of rural urban migration is happening because of nature of migration is temporary or seasonal. This type of migration helps the migrants to increase the flow of remittances mainly from non - farm activities in urban location, which is easily available. This creates a demand for income generating opportunity in non - farm activities rather than agricultural income, although these temporary migrants are living in rural areas

E. *Gardner Katy & Ahmed Zahir (2006)*

Place, Social Protection & Migration in Bangladesh – A Londoni Village in Biswanath: The paper highlights on the relationship between migration, poverty and social protection in an area of Bangladesh where the rate of migration towards London is very high. These migrants are able to create a socio economic impact during their short or long stay in their respective places. Their investment increases the livelihoods conditions and provides the poor people some kind of social protection. This not only help the poor in that region but it also attracts the people from other regions where this kind of economic development is absent due to lack of international migration. Thus, the paper suggests that this migration nature not only benefit the society at large, but it also provide the desired social protection, that the poor people are looking for.

F. *Katseli T. Louka, Lucas E.B. Robert & Xenogiani Theodora (2006)*

Effects of Migration on Sending Countries: The paper tries to develop the synergies between migration and development. The paper focuses on the issue that how migration can be managed so as to maximize the net gain, both for sending countries as well as receiving countries. It was also observed that the case of migration is not only income driven but also geographic proximity related. Moreover common language also created equal impact on rural urban migration.

G. Ministry of education(MOE)-2020), MHRD-2013

There is sheer distinction among the higher education institution in terms of providing quality education.

III. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Although there are various methods of conducting research, researchers notes that there are two general and basic method of conducting research. The quantitative research method focuses on seeking in –depth numerical analysis in a formal rigid structure, versus the qualitative approach which focuses on understanding the opinions and behavioral responses of the subject. The qualitative approach enables the researcher to obtain a deep rooted interpretation of the individual’s personal experiences through their respective responses. This method will then prove to be appropriate in that it will allow the researcher to gain the views and opinions of individuals in relation to their understanding of migration of the students following which a massive brain drain is going on.

This is basically an empirical study based on the data from educational institutions, State Universities and lay out of educational reports, published research papers and West Bengal Government Education Department, Ministry of higher education and news papers information. Primarily survey research method was applied for making the project more qualitative and quantitative by using relevant and considerable data. In fact, primary and secondary data were used to make the project more accurate. A comprehensive questionnaire was prepared to collect the appropriate and necessary data from 350(approx) respondents. The hypotheses were calculated by using regression analysis. The results revealed that all the independent variables (such as, inadequate educational facilities, less infrastructure facilities, in appropriate systems of teaching and learning process (blending), non availability experienced, knowledgeable and qualified academicians, less Training and grooming facilities, lack of proper placement, inappropriate ambiences and above all unstructured government plan and policy to the issue) had a positive impact on the dependent variables (trend for migration following which the major brain drain)

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN

The technique semi structured interviews was employed to obtain data within this research. This is one of the main techniques used under the qualitative research stream. In our everyday lives, we often tend to forget how to listen properly. In conducting a semi-structured interview, the interviewer is interested in finding out or understanding the subjects’ point of view, experiences and therefore ought to pay attention and listen to what the subject has to say whilst being objective at the same time

The data is taken from secondary sources. The data is taken from many authenticated websites and organizations like Government news bulletin, Ministry of Education. West

Bengal State Government Education Reports., MHRD. This research paper is also written with the help of many other research papers which are written by professionals.

V. CONCLUSION

In rural Bengal, It has become a trend to go to another state for higher education. This contributes significantly to brain drain and loss of human capital. The state government needs to consider the major loss of human capacity of the state in the context of student’s prospects. The government should direct the institutions such as professional schools to waive the fees of the best and topper students and waive the fees for under privileged and lower middle class students so that they can pursue the higher studies in which they are interested. The result of this work shows that family and neighborhood are the main sources of information dissemination to rural students and have a great influence on students where to study. The study also shows why students from rural areas of Bengal prefer to study outside the state to find a good living that is not available in their home town. In order to prevent the trend of out-migration of students, the state government along with the all institutions, colleges and Universities should create an environment that does not impose high costs on students and allows them to continue their students in West Bengal. Therefore, the state government should well aware that education institutions prepare students for the future; they must leverage technology to impart education and give a sense of professionalism. If possible setting up new colleges for professional courses, and recruit the best possible experienced teachers. This is high time to give a second thought to the most important issues for the sake of the state. Let’s hope the state will thrive for the slogan- “No brain drain further, let’s go only for brain gain”

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest

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